

**KIMYO FANIDA SUYUQLIKLARNI EKSTRAKSIYALASHNING
UMUMIY TUSHUNCHALARI**

**Mamajonova Sitora Uyg'unjon qizi,
Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani
2 son politexnikumi kimyo fani o'qituvchisi**

Annotasiya: Maqolada Eritmalar yoki kattik jismlar tarkibidan bir yoki bir necha komionentlarni eripichilar yordamida ajratib olish jarayoni ekstraksiyalash ekanligi xaqida tushuntirish bilan birga bu jarayonning umumiy tushunchalari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kimyo, suyuqlik, tur, material, ekstraksiya, komponent

Eritmalar yoki kattik jismlar tarkibidan bir yoki bir necha komponentlarni erituvchilar yordamida ajratib olish jarayoni ekstraksiyalash deb ataladi. Bu jarayon, ikki turga bo'linadi:

- a) Suyuqliklarni ekstraksiyalash;
- b) kattik materiallarni ekstraksiyalash.

Eritmalar tarkibidan bir yoki bir necha komionentlarni tanlab ta'sir kiluvchi erituvchilar — ekstragentlar yordamida ajratib olish jarayoni suyuqliklarni ekstraksiyalash deb yuritiladi.

Suyuq aralashma bilan erituvchi uzaro aralashtirilganda erituvchida fakat kerakli komponentlar yaxshi eriydi, kolgan komponentlar esa juda yomon yoki butunlay erimaydi. Ekstraksiyalash jarayon xam rektifikasiyalash kabi suyuqlik aralashmalarini ajratish uchun ishlatiladi. Bu usullarning kaysi birini tanlash aralashmalar tarkibidagi moddalarning xossalariga boglik.

Rektifikasiyalash jarayoni odatda issiklik ta'sirida boradi. Ekstraksiyalashni amalga oshirish uchun issiklik talab etilmaydi. Rektifikasiyalash aralashma komponentlarining x,ar' xil uchuvchanliklariga asoslanadi. Agar aralashma

komponentlarining kaynash temperaturasi bir-biriga yaqin yoki ular yuqori temperaturaga bekaror bo'lsa, bunday xollarda ekstraksiyalash jarayonidan foydalaniladi. Tanlab olingan erituvchining zichligi ekstraksiyalanishi lozim bo'lgan suyuqlik zichligidan kam bo'lishi shart. Dastlabki eritma va erituvchi o'zaro ta'sir ettirilganda ikkita faza (ekstrakt va rafinat) xosil bo'ladi. Ajratib olingan moddaning erituvchidagi eritmasi ekstrakt, dastlabki eritmaning qoldig'i esa rafinat deb yuritiladi. Rafinat tarkibida biroz miqdorda erituvchi ham bo'ladi. Olingan ikkita suyuqlik fazasi (ekstrakt va rafinat) bir-biridan tindirish, syentrifugalash yoki boshqa mexanik usullar yordamida ajratiladi.

So'ngra ekstrakt tarkibidan tegishli maxsulot ajratib olinadi, rafinatdan esa erituvchi regenerasiya qilinadi. Suyuqliklarni ekstraksiyalash boshqa usullar (rektifikasiyalash, buglatish va xokazo) ga nisbatan birmuncha afazalliklarga ega: jarayon past temperaturada olib boriladi, eritmaning bug'lanishi uchun issiqliktalab qilinmaydi, yuqori tanlovchanlik xususiyatiga ega bo'lgan istalgan erituvchini ishlatish imkoni bor. Bu usul kamchilikdan xoli emas; qo'shimcha komponent (erituvchi) ni ishlatish va uni regenerasiya qilishni tashkil etish apparatlar sxemasini murakkablashtiradi va ekstraksiyalash jarayonini qimmatlashtiradi.

Suyuqlik sistemalarini ekstraksiyalash jarayonlari kimyo, neftni kayta ishlash, neft kimyosi va sanoatning boshqa tarmoqlarida keng ishlatiladi. Bu jarayonlar turli organik va neftkimyoviy sintez maxsulotlarini toza xolda ajratib olish, nodir va kam tarqalgan elementlarni olish va ularni ajratish, chiqindi suvlarini tozalash va shu kabi boshqa bir qator ishlarni amalga oshirish uchun ishlatiladi. Ayrim sharoitlarda ekstraksiyalash jarayoni rektifikasiyalash bilan birgalikda olib boriladi. Suyuqlik aralashmasi rektifikasiyalashdan oldin birlamchi ekstraksiyalash yuli bilan kieman ajratilsa, rektifikasiyalash uchun issiqlik xarajatlari ancha kamayadi.

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